

READ ME

MATERIALS USE GUIDELINES

- This document was developed specifically for evaluation of statements on **racial equity**. Special considerations should be made when these materials are to be applied more broadly for content related to "diversity, equity, and inclusion".
- These materials are considered a work in progress. We are always reviewing and updating our processes and content in an evidence-based manner. New versions will be made available online.
- We encourage open use and sharing of these materials and kindly request that the following citation be used:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6385709>.

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Review - Racial Equity Essay

Instructions: You will want to be familiar with the resources/guidelines that were provided to the applicants. These can be found on the OHSU Vollum Institute/Neuroscience Graduate Program (NGP) website under the “[What makes a good racial equity essay](#)” dropdown. Below is the essay prompt and the scoring rubric, followed by a section on “red flags” which should supplement the rubric scoring system with examples.

On pages 4-5 of this document you will find three example racial equity essays which were constructed after online research by staff of the Vollum Institute Racial Equity & Inclusion Center. Keeping in mind the resources/guidelines provided to the applicants, use the rubric and “red flags” supplemental information to score all three essays. Make a note of your rationale for why each essay received its score. Bring your score and notes to our workshop session where we will discuss and answer questions that arose during this process.

*The developed rubric was inspired by and adapted from materials provided online through [UC Berkeley’s Office of Faculty Equity & Welfare](#)

*The material on “Red flags” was adapted from: <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/campus/diversity-statements-what-avoid-and-what-include>

Prompt: In your racial equity essay, we would like for you to share your perspective on what the NGP racial equity statement means to the training environment for our graduate students and faculty. What is your interpretation of what we aim to achieve in pursuing racial equity within the NGP? Also, please describe how you could contribute personally to the NGP racial equity goals.

Understanding the Challenges & Getting Involved w/ Racial Equity in STEM	
Score = Unsatisfactory	Unaware or disbelief of systemic challenges & the system of racism (no signs they went to the links we provided)
	Unaware or disbelief of personal racism (individual values, beliefs, thoughts, & prejudices that harm members of PEER communities)
	Largely avoids the topic of racism (may bring up race but avoids talking about racism)
	Little expressed knowledge of the topic (no signs they went to the links we provided)
	Lack of interest/Personal responsibility
Score = Satisfactory	Essays show aspects of unsatisfactory scores as well as excellent scores
Score = Excellent	Expressed knowledge of individual/systemic challenges and why the work is important
	Discusses the topic and shows depth of understanding (e.g., concepts like equity/inclusion/systems)
	Demonstrates interest in the topic or willingness to learn
	Describes current involvement and/or clear ideas on potential to act

Red flags: Common mistakes or pitfalls when writing the racial equity statement may fall into three major categories:

- Diversity by proxy
- Personal stories disconnected from larger systemic issues
- Avoidance with the topic/talking about race

1. Diversity by proxy

Diversity by proxy is when applicants borrow from the success of others around them, an organization or program. The applicant may speak specifically about their department's demographics or a program for people of color that they have **minimally** interacted with.

Example 1: "____ (university's name) is one of the most diverse campuses in the country. We are ____% white, ____% Latin, ____% Asian/Pacific Islander, ____% African American."

Example 2: Applicants might mention success and claim some responsibility for other people of color due to their passive engagement. "During senior year in undergrad I tutored at the Student Services Center and we have had many wonderful, bright students of color who just need intense mentorship. Due to the mentorship that they received in the Center, now these students are successfully in graduate programs"

Example 3: The message of "I support success for people of color" can be followed by surprise and/or self-congratulation. "I went to a high school with many disadvantaged students and a couple of them have gone on to grad programs at very good schools!"; or "I had one Black professor in college who was impressively articulate and actually turned out to be the best math teacher I've ever had!"

We call this "diversity by proxy" because the applicant's example relies on numbers that tell us about where they are and not who they are or what they have done. Secondly, they are borrowing identity, status and achievement by linking themselves to the success stories of students or faculty of color. In this way, they give undue credit to themselves as a savior.

2. Personal stories disconnected from larger systemic issues

Applicants write of personal experiences that have occurred in their personal life that are meant to reflect their appreciation for diversity and inclusion and their dissatisfaction with racism without discussing the larger systemic issues.

Example 1: They may write about an event that solidified their understanding of privilege: "I grew up in a small town where there was only one Indian family and one of the girls from that family became a close friend. And then, in the sixth grade, everything changed. She and I both auditioned for the school play, *Annie*, and it was clear that another girl got the lead because she was white and looked the part. But my friend was clearly better than everyone else. I felt bad for her but there was nothing I could do. And that is why I really feel so strongly about racism and exclusion and do what I can to help students of color."

Example 2: They may also talk about how they work with and learn so much from students of color. The focus is only on their feelings and how they assuage their feelings of social injustice by their engagement with people of color rather than consideration or engagement with broader systemic issues.

3. Avoidance of the topic/talking about racism specifically

Applicants write that they are in favor of diversity and inclusion but show no current or future initiative for engaging in racial equity issues, OR largely avoids discussing race in general.

Example 1: “Diversity is important in science but I haven’t had much time to think about these issues yet.”

Example 2: “Diversity is important but I haven't had much exposure” and then fails to provide any evidence of having informed themselves or avoid discussing any future initiative to inform themselves.

Example 3: “I believe in diversity, but there’s not much I can do as a student because I have not been in a position where I might make decisions. I would be supportive if there were some people of color.”

Example 4: “I think diversity is important. I myself am a woman who is marginalized in science.” (or applicants discuss the issues/needs of other marginalized groups without saying anything about racism and systemic racism).

Example 5: “Diversity is good but people should get in based on merit”.

These red flags suggest that impact can only be made from certain positions, thereby exonerating most people who do not go against the grain. This obscures the roles that everyone plays in maintaining the status quo and contributing in small and large ways to discriminatory practices and negative outcomes for faculty, staff and students of color.

EXAMPLE ESSAY 1

As I read through this prompt, one memory came through with bright clarity. “Oh god! Do not invite him to come along with us! He might try to kiss one of us!”, said one of my former male classmates. His comment was about me. I went to school in a rural area and came out as gay during high school. Although a few of my close friends did not change the way they treated me, I still experienced hatred directed at me because of who I am. Coming out was a big decision for me and I spent a lot of time deciding whether I should do it. I knew how many people in my town viewed being gay or lesbian and I was terrified to have that hate directed towards me. I was mortified when my former classmate made the assumption that I would kiss him just because I was gay. I spent a lot of time regretting my decision for coming out and desperately wanted to graduate so I could move away. Luckily for me, I had an incredibly supportive friend group that would remind me that nothing had changed with our friendship. They are the reason I was able to graduate, move, and go to a state-college. Although my experience at a state-college was different, I still experienced homophobia and sometimes struggled to fit in. My interpretation of the NGP’s Racial Equity Statement is that the program is interested in increasing more student diversity. Because of my experience, I can proudly say that I am in support of more diversity in academia.

As I mentioned before, I was born and raised in a small town that didn’t have much diversity. Almost all of the students in my elementary, middle, and high school were White. When I was growing up, my parents did not talk about race and told me that it was rude to ever mention it. I grew up with all White friends and it never occurred to me that I had little experience working with or getting to know people from different races until I went to college. Even though I made friends with people from different races, I didn’t learn that there was still a major issue in America until the protests last summer. Like many people, the summer protests represented the first time that I learned about systemic racism.

Since the summer protest I’ve tried to learn more about racism and I believe I still have so much to learn. One feature of the training program at OHSU is that the program has taken diversity seriously. Even though I may not know a lot about this topic, I believe that this training environment will help me learn more about race and racism. I think that this is a unique program feature that sets OHSU apart from other graduate programs and I am excited to take advantage of the opportunities that are provided! I would like to enroll in the racial equity course in order to learn more about what I do not know. In addition, I would like to attend seminars that the program offers and contribute to an overall better environment for other students. I know what being singled out feels like and I want to contribute to an environment where every student feels welcomed.

EXAMPLE ESSAY 2

My own cultural competency is built on a lifetime of international experiences. I grew up on the Galapagos Islands, later attended high school in Nairobi, Kenya and I now visit my parents annually in New Zealand. Growing up surrounded by cultures different from my own, I was encouraged to identify and value both the commonalities and differences of the human experience. As a college student, exposure to diverse peoples was instrumental in shaping my worldview and values and from growing up overseas, I know what it feels like to find oneself outside the dominant culture. In science the widespread image of a scientist is: an older, white male who works in a lab. This pervasive image may be discouraging for students who do not “fit in” based on their own identities. Throughout my education, I have benefited from the privilege of being a white male in the field. My identity means that people do not automatically discount my credibility when they first meet me, that I have never heard degrading comments like “you don’t look like an electrophysiologist,” and that I am constantly on the positive side of unconscious biases when it comes to small things like how the quality of my work is judged by others and more significant things like the likelihood of gaining/maintaining a job. These patterns of exclusion are not only unjust; they also limit the range of perspectives that can contribute to the field of science overall.

I am inspired by the racial equity statement that the Vollum Institute/Neuroscience Graduate Program has created. It represents the idea that the directors believe that a racially inclusive environment is a necessary component of prosperous research and training programs. It is clear the Vollum Institute/Neuroscience Graduate Program is working

to address “policies, practices, and attitudes that reinforce (or fail to eliminate) differential outcomes based on race”, whether that has to do with the admissions process, hiring practices, pay, and dealing with conflict. Becoming an anti-racist organization is so much more than how people relate to each other when those people’s beliefs may creep into the work and affect others around them.

As an NGP student, I would like to build on my previous experiences in fostering diversity, equity, and inclusion. During undergrad at UC San Diego, I frequently supported the Society for Women in Graduate Studies in Physiology (SWIGS) which has many goals that promote a diverse environment, such as increasing the awareness about gender bias in STEM fields and encouraging the next generation of female scientists through outreach activities. What I observed through those activities was a lack of racial diversity within SWIGS. I have learned that promoting diversity goes well beyond improving gender equity, and must include enabling opportunities and support for underrepresented minority women as well. The mission of the Alliance for Visible Diversity in Science (AVDS) really speaks to me. I appreciate that this group of students exists to come together for a very focused purpose of “increasing racial and ethnic equity within research at OHSU”. I would be interested to lend my voice and helping hand to AVDS in whatever way I could support them with their mission. More specifically, I would like to work within AVDS to build bridges with other groups that could (and should) take a more intersectional approach by incorporating racial equity as a core part of their efforts.

EXAMPLE ESSAY 3

Firstly, I want to commend the NGP on their approach to addressing the lack of diversity in science. As a woman in science, I have experienced the hardship of being the only one in the room. I have firsthand experience of being talked over and overlooked which has created challenges for my personal confidence and feeling like an imposter in scientific spaces. Because of this experience, I understand how important it is for us to make space for diverse voices. If people feel welcomed and valued, they can reach their full potential. I believe diversity encompasses more than just race and we should be thinking about how we can create space for everyone.

I value fairness, compassion, and hard work. These values guide my approach and understanding of diversity. I believe everyone should have the opportunity to work in an environment that is welcoming, and we should all be treated with fairness and compassion. This will enable us to showcase the best of our abilities through our own hard work.

I have been lucky enough to be exposed to a diverse range of people throughout my life. I had several neighbors who were people of color (POC), and as such was exposed to different languages and cultures. This taught me that there is more than one way of doing things and really drove home how we are all unique and have something valuable to contribute. In addition, my undergrad institution was very diverse. I had friends who were POCs, friends that identified as non-binary and friends who came from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. The exposure and experience have enabled me to effectively communicate with people from varying backgrounds. I believe that this will be an advantage in the NGP’s goal of increasing diversity.